

PAYVANDLASH BIRIKMASINI HISOBLASH USLUBIYOTI.

Abduxakim Nigmatovich Abdullayev

t.f.n., PhD., Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti
“Texnologiya va professional ta’lim metodikasi” kafedrası dotsenti.

Baratova Fazilat Saidovna

professional ta’lim fakulteti TT-301 guruh talabasi

Rajapbayeva Sevinch Aybek qizi

professional ta’lim fakulteti TT-302 guruh talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14974259>

Annotatsiya: Yoyli payvandlash uchun yoyning uzluksiz yonishi va chok materialini atrof-muhitning zararli ta’sirlaridan himoyasini ta’minlovchi turli surtmali yoki qoplamali elektrodlar qo’llaniladi.

Kalit so’zlar: Yoy, payvand, chok, qoplama, elektrodlar, birikma, elektroyoyli, avtomatik, material, *joiz kuchlanish*, metall, cho’zilish.

Annotatsiya: Для дуговой сварки применяются различные покрытия или диэлектрические электроды, которые обеспечивают непрерывное горение дуги и защищают свариваемый материал от вредных воздействий окружающей среды.

Ключевые слова: Дуга, сварка, сварной шов, покрытие, электроды, соединение, электросварной, автоматический, материал, допустимое напряжение, металл, удлинение.

Annotation: For arc welding, various coated or coated electrodes are used, which ensure continuous arc burning and protect the weld material from harmful environmental influences.

Key words: Arc, weld, weld, coating, electrodes, joint, electric arc, automatic, material, permissible stress, metal, elongation.

Natijalar: Payvandlash birikmasini hisoblash uslubiyoti. 1 Payvandlashni hisoblash quyidagi tartibda olib boriladi. 1) *Payvandlash usuli tanlanadi* (dastaki, elektroyoyli, avtomatik va b.) yoki topshiriqqa muvofiq belgilanadi.

2) *Elektrod turi va payvandlanayotgan detallar materiali tanlab olinadi (yoki topshiriqqa muvofiq belgilanadi)*. Yoyli payvandlash uchun yoyning uzluksiz yonishi va chok materialini atrof-muhitning zararli ta’sirlaridan himoyasini ta’minlovchi turli surtmali yoki qoplamali elektrodlar qo’llaniladi. Konstruksion po’latlarni payvandlash uchun E42, E42A, E46, E46A, E50, E50A va boshqa elektrodlar qo’llaniladi. E harfidan keyingi 10 ga ko’paytirilgan son Mpa da o’lchanadigan chok metalli qarshiligining minimal qiymatini anglatadi. A harfi

esa chok metallining yuqori plastik xossalriga erishishni ta'minlovchi elektrodning sifatini bildiradi.

3) *Asosiy material va payvand chok materiali uchun joiz kuchlanish aniqlanadi.*

Asosiy metall cho'zilishining joiz kuchlanishi:

$$[\sigma_R] = \sigma_T / [s], \tag{1}$$

MUHOKAMA: bu erda σ_T — asosiy metallning oquvchanlik chegarasi; $[s]$ – mustahkamlik zaxirasining joiz koeffisienti ($[s] = 1,2... 1,8$ kam uglerodli po'latlar uchun va $[s] = 1,5... 2,2$ legirlangan po'latlar uchun) — xomaki hisoblashlarda qiymati; agar buzilish og'ir oqibatlar bilan kechsa, u holda $[s]$ qiymati 1,5-2 marta ortadi.

XULOSA:

Statik yuklamada payvandlangan chok uchunlar joiz kuchlanish $[\sigma']$ asosiy metall cho'zilishiga joiz kuchlanish $[\sigma_R]$ ulushida belgilanadi (1-jadval)

1-jadval

Payvandlash jarayonining texnologiyasi	Choklardagi joiz kuchlanish		
	cho'zilishda $[\sigma'_R]$	siqilishda $[\sigma'_{SJ}]$	qirqilishda $[\tau']$
Flyus ostida avtomatik, E42A va E50A elektrodleri bilan dastaki, kontaktli tutash payvand	$[\sigma_R]$	$[\sigma_R]$	$0,65 \cdot [\sigma_R]$
E42 va E50 yoyli elektrodler bilan dastaki, gazli payvandlash	$0,9 \cdot [\sigma_R]$	$[\sigma_R]$	$0,6 \cdot [\sigma_R]$

Agar turli mexanik xossalarga ega detallar payvandlansa, u holda joiz kuchlanishlarni hisoblash oquvchanlik chegarasi eng kam qiymatli material uchun amalga oshiriladi.

4) *Birikmaning hisoblash sxemasi tuziladi,* bunda u sxema ko'rinishiga keltiriladi. Birikmaga ta'sir qiluvchi tashqi kuchlarni nazariy mexanika qoidalariga mos ravishda payvandlangan chok og'irlik markaziga o'tkazish lozim, bundan tashqari, payvand choklar tekisligiga burchak ostida ta'sir qiluvchi kuchlarni perpendikulyar qismlarga taqsimlash zarur bo'ladi (1-rasm).

1-rasm.

F_1 kuchlarni o'tkazishda parallel ravishda kuchi $M = F_1 \cdot l$ ga teng qo'shimcha moment juftliklar paydo bo'ladi.

F_2 kuchlarni o'tkazishda ta'sir chizig'i bo'ylab hech qanday qo'shimcha kuch va momentlar paydo bo'lmaydi.

Masalada barabanga arqondan kuchlanish tirgakka nisbatan nosimmetrik joylashgan, shuning uchun payvand choklarga ta'sir qiluvchi kuchlar ham (R_1 va R_2) turlicha bo'ladi. Ularni aniqlash uchun 1 va 2 tayanchlar - tirgaklarga nisbatan muvozanat tenglamalarini tuzish kerak.

$$\sum M_i = 0; \sum P_i = 0.$$

Masalada aylanish o'qiga nisbatan g'ildirak muvozanati shartidan:

$$\sum T_i = \sum F_i \cdot \frac{D_i}{2} = 0$$

D_i ning tegishli diametrlarida choklar kesilishini keltirib chiqaruvchi F_i kuchlanishni aniqlash talab qilinadi.

Masalalar uchun hisoblash sxemalaridan namunalar 2-rasmda keltirilgan.

2-rasm

5) *Chok katetlari belgilanadi.* Ko'p hollarda $k = \delta_{min}$, bu erda δ_{min} — payvandlanayotgan detallarning eng kichik qalinligi. Texnologiya sharti bo'yicha agar $\delta_{min} \geq 3$ mm bo'lsa, $k \geq 3$ mm,. Katetning maksimal qiymati chegaralanmaydi, lekin $k > 20$ mm choklar kam qo'llaniladi.

6) *Har bir kuch omili (kuch, moment) uchun alohida ta'sir qiluvchi kuchlanish aniqlanadi.* Kuchlanish jamlashda ularning yo'nalishi hisobga olinadi (agar vektorlar yo'nalishi ustma-ust tushsa, u holda ular algebraik qo'shiladi, agar vektorlar perpendikulyar bo'lsa, u holda ular geometrik qo'shiladi).

7) *Payvandlangan choklarni loyihalashda,* odatda, mustahkamlik shartidan ularning uzunligi aniqlanadi. Bunda yon choklar uzunligi $50k$ dan katta emas deb olinadi, pesh choklar esa ixtiyoriy uzunlikda bo'lishi mumkin. Burchak chokining

l_{min} minimal uzunligi 30 mm ni tashkil qiladi, bu payvand choklar nuqsonlarini yopib turadi.

$F = 25$ kN kuch bilan cho'zilayotgan, qalinligi $\delta = 5,0$ mm va kengligi $a = 100$ mm ikkita po'lat listni ilmoqsimon biriktirish uchun umumiy payvandlangan chok l ning uzunligini aniqlang. Payvandlangan chokdagi joiz kuchlanish $[\tau] = 60$ MPa.

Yechish

1. Pesh chok qirqimi yuzasi:

$$S_l = a \cdot 0,7 \cdot \delta$$

2. Yon choklar qirqimi yuzasi:

$$S_f = 2 \cdot x \cdot 0,7 \cdot \delta$$

3. Payvandlangan birikmaning mustahkamlik sharti :

$$\tau = F / (S_l + S_f) \leq [\tau]$$

4. Payvandlangan choklarning umumiy uzunligi:

$$l = (a + 2 \cdot x) = F / (0,7 \cdot \delta \cdot [\tau])$$

5. Yon chok uzunligi:

$$x = (l - a) / 2.$$

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Abdullayev.A.N (2024). Use of measuring instruments. v international bulletin of engineering and technology (113–119). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10726900>
2. Abdullayev.A.N (2024). A study of enclosed cylindrical and bevel gear reducers. Nauka i innovatsiya, 2(6), 148–154. <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/si/article/view/28348>
3. Abdullayev.A.N (2023). Methodology of problem solving in technical mechanics classes. Scientific electronic magazine "Science and Education". Volume 4 Issue 4 https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GJzuiTGK_ITj7HReL8Pl6_yMqytgpgj1/view?usp=share_link. ISSN 2181-0842 . APRIL 2023 . 684-688
4. A.N.Abdullayev. "Innovations in the field of pedagogical technologies of teaching in technical higher education institutions" Republic-wide scientific and technical conference on "Modern research, innovations, current problems and

development trends of techniques and technologies" April 8-9, 2022, pp. 336-339 Jizzakh polytechnic institute

5. A.N. Abdullayev. "Universal stand for laboratory and practical classes in electrical engineering". Collection of materials of the scientific-practical conference on the topic "The role of young scientists of higher and secondary special, vocational educational institutions in the innovative development of agriculture". TashDAU, Tashkent-2016, 382-386

6. A.N.Abdullayev. "Development of production serving farms" problems and solutions to increase the export potential of the agricultural sector, to organize multi-sectoral farms, to develop the production and market infrastructure serving them, April 27 2019 TDAU

